

Decision-support tools for integrating cross-cutting issues

* Indicates required question

1. Tool name *

If more than one tool is discussed in each paper, complete the form for each tool individually.

2. Nexus links *

choose EXPLICIT if the nexus factor is directly referenced; choose IMPLICIT if the nexus relationship is clearly relevant but the nexus language may not be used.

Check all that apply.

- food - explicit
- food - implicit
- water - explicit
- water - implicit
- health - explicit
- health - implicit
- climate - explicit
- climate - implicit
- biodiversity - explicit
- biodiversity - implicit

3. Nexus links analyzed *

Beyond mentioning nexus elements, did this tool analyze nexus elements?

Check all that apply.

- none
- food
- water
- health
- climate
- biodiversity

4. Key influencers of implementation *

Check all that apply.

- Intergovernmental organizations
- (Sub-)national governments
- NGOs and donors
- Private sector
- Unknown
- Other: _____

5. Scale *

Global includes more than one continent; Supranational includes more than one country on the same continent [from Values Assessment Table 6.2]

Mark only one oval.

- global
- Supranational
- National
- Subnational
- Multiple

6. Capacity *

From Values Assessment Figure 6.4:

Motivational capacities ensure that stakeholders (both individuals and organizations) have awareness of, and desire to, consider diverse values in decisions. Motivational capacities are strongly embedded into the cultural, economic, institutional and policy context (Balmford, 2002; Cormier & Gordon, 2001; Kent & Myers, 2001; Young, 2002). Motivation can have intrinsic sources (e.g., sense of meaning, internalized norms and social conventions, which are often rooted in socio-cultural relations and worldviews), and extrinsic sources (e.g., rewards or punishments, which can be established by formal rules and policy instruments) (Ryan & Deci, 2000), although organization studies found that intrinsic motivation is more strongly linked to positive attitudes and work performance (Gagné & Deci, 2005; Lawler & Hall, 1970; Schreurs et al., 2014).

Analytical capacities help select and use suitable tools to acquire and synthesise all necessary information on diverse values. Scientific methods – and valuation tools – carry a cognitive representation of the world, a theorization of action, and give legitimacy to specific values and perspectives (Cabane & Tantchou, 2016; Carolan, 2009; Desrosières, 1998; Lascoumes & Le Galès, 2005). The relation between knowledge and decision-making is not straightforward or self-evident (Dessai et al., 2009; Dilling & Lemos, 2011; Matzek et al., 2014; Pullinger, 2014; Sutherland et al., 2014; Wesselink et al., 2013). To recognize and consider the nature's diverse values in decisions, valuation needs to be inclusive towards different forms of scientific and non-scientific knowledge (Cash et al., 2003; Mauser et al., 2013; Robertson & Hull, 2001).

Bridging capacities provide a pluralistic, value-based perspective to problem-oriented decision-making that bring together different ways of knowing and doing in a co-learning process. Facilitation is a crucial element of co-producing legitimate and credible knowledge for decision-making (Breslow, 2015; Kok et al., 2017; Lemos & Morehouse, 2005; Peterson et al., 2003; Turnhout, 2018; Voinov & Bousquet, 2010).

Negotiation capacities, targeted both at the individual and the organization level, can broaden the process of negotiation from enforcement to relationship building and cooperation (Fairman et al., 2012; Soliman & Antheaume, 2017), and therefore help navigating trade-offs between the values and interests of different stakeholders (de Magalhães et al., 2019). Negotiation capacities are also crucial in situations where trade-offs lead to conflicts among contrasting groups of winners and losers (Butler et al., 2013; Kovács et al., 2015; McShane et al., 2011; Turkelboom et al., 2018).

Social networking capacities support learning (Armitage et al., 2011; Bartlett et al., 2012; Reed et al., 2014), adapting (Simha et al., 2017) and acting together (Berkes, 2009; Reed et al., 2017). A governance system that builds on strong networks can effectively use social mechanisms (e.g., collective sanctions, social memory) to adapt, coordinate, and safeguard exchanges (Jones et al., 1997) and therefore can increase regional resilience (Luthe et al., 2012).

Governance capacities allow effectively resolving problems and fulfilling the needs of citizens by mobilizing resources, making decisions via analytic and deliberative functions, and implementing decisions via coordination and regulation (Christensen et al., 2016; Dang et al., 2016; Tan, 2019). Improving governance capacities contributes to good governance (Rothstein & Teorell, 2012), and ensures that fair policies and institutions exist, and decisions incorporate the values held by different stakeholders in an accountable, transparent, and reflexive way (González & Healey, 2005; van der Molen, 2018) (Annex 6.1).

Check all that apply.

- Motivational capacity
- Analytical capacity
- Bridging capacity
- Negotiation capacity
- Social network capacity

Governance capacity

7. Tool family *

[IPBES standardized typology of policy support tools and methodologies:](#)

Assembling data and knowledge (including monitoring) addresses underlying scientific and other types of knowledge gaps (including indigenous and local knowledge) by providing the data necessary to understand the function and dynamics of biodiversity, human wellbeing, nature's contributions to people (including ecosystem goods and services), and associated social-ecological systems. This includes, among others, data collection efforts, databases and monitoring, indicators, oral history, mapping of ecosystem services. This family is relevant to all elements of the policy cycle.

Assessment and evaluation addresses existing scientific and other knowledge by synthesizing and assessing such knowledge types (including indigenous and local knowledge) relative to the status, function, determinants/drivers and outlook for specific aspects of nature, nature's contributions to people, human well-being, relevant social-ecological systems and outcomes, as well as the connections between these. These include different types of assessment and evaluation tools, based on a variety of methods and diverse conceptualizations of values of nature, nature's contributions to people, and a good quality of life. This family is relevant to all elements of the policy cycle.

Public discussion, involvement and participatory process contribute to identifying problems and opportunities, setting goals and priorities, meeting agreed principles such as gender and social equity, establishing the case for policy action and building shared understanding of requirements and consequences. This is achieved by supporting discussion and deliberation about the implications of new knowledge and data, emerging risks and opportunities, potential societal responses, as well as the effectiveness and merits of existing and potential institutions and policy settings. This family is relevant to all elements of the policy cycle.

Selection and design of policy instruments supports the identification, evaluation and choice of potential policies and institutional settings, including evaluation and comparisons of past experience or similar experience elsewhere, as well as outcomes under different policies and circumstances and policy mix analysis. It focuses primarily on the choice and design of new and existing policies, keeping in mind that policy instruments are distinct from policy support tools and methodologies. This family is primarily aligned with Policy Design and Decisions, but it could be relevant to the other two elements of the policy cycle.

Implementation, outreach and enforcement support practical implementation of policies, including laws, regulations and quasi-regulations, economic instruments and incentives, as well as information tools, including through monitoring, providing information to stakeholders and through supporting enforcement and compliance activities. This family focuses primarily on supporting the implementation of policies that have already been decided and enacted. It is primarily aligned with Policy Implementation, but could be relevant to the other two elements of the policy cycle.

Training and capacity-building identify and address capacity gaps and shortfalls by enhancing the skills and capacity of relevant actors and organizations, including Government officials and agencies, communities and representatives, businesses, non-government organizations, advisors and support services. This family is cross-cutting to all elements and can be applied within each element to enhance capacity and improve outcomes.

Social learning, innovation and adaptive governance address gaps and disconnects in the policy process, by identifying opportunities to promote social learning and to strengthen links and feedback mechanisms across elements and activities, supporting improved responsiveness, risk management and overall performance of policy process as a whole. This family is cross-cutting to all elements, but applied to the links and inter-relationships across elements and activities to influence the dynamics and performance of the policy review, development and implementation process itself.

Check all that apply.

- Assembling data and knowledge (including monitoring)
- Assessment and evaluation
- Public discussion, involvement, and participatory process
- Selection and design of policy instruments
- Implementation, outreach, and enforcement
- Training and capacity building
- Social learning, innovation, and adaptive governance

8. Biome / 'anthrome' *

IPBES standardized 17 Units of Analysis for the Global Assessment in four biomes/'anthromes' (See [IPBES Global Assessment Chapter 2.2, pg. 255](#)):

Terrestrial: Tropical and subtropical dry and humid forests; Temperate and boreal forests and woodlands; Mediterranean forests, woodlands and scrub; Arctic and mountain tundra; Tropical and subtropical grasslands; Temperate grasslands; Deserts and xeric shrublands; Cryosphere

Inland and freshwaters: Wetlands; Inland surface waters and water bodies

Ocean: Shelf ecosystems; Surface open ocean; Deep sea; Coastal areas

Anthromes: Urban and semiurban areas; Cultivated areas; Aquaculture areas; Coastal areas intensively used by humans

Check all that apply.

- Terrestrial
- Inland and fresh waters
- Ocean
- 'Anthromes'
- Unspecified

9. NCPs *

[IPBES standardized](#)

Habitat creation and maintenance: The formation and continued production, by ecosystems or organisms within them, of ecological conditions necessary or favorable for living beings of direct or indirect importance to humans. E.g. growing sites for plants, nesting, feeding, and mating sites for animals, resting and overwintering areas for migratory mammals, birds and butterflies, roosting places for agricultural pests and disease vectors, nurseries for juvenile stages of fish, habitat creation at different soil depths by invertebrates

Pollination and dispersal of seeds and other propagules: Facilitation by animals of movement of pollen among flowers, and dispersal of seeds, larvae or spores of organisms beneficial or harmful to humans

Regulation of air quality: Regulation (by impediment or facilitation) by ecosystems, of CO₂/O₂ balance, O₃, sulphur oxide, nitrogen oxides (NO_x), volatile organic compounds (VOC), particulates, aerosols, allergens; Filtration, fixation, degradation or storage of pollutants that directly affect human health or infrastructure

Regulation of climate: Climate regulation by ecosystems (including regulation of global warming) through: Positive or negative effects on emissions of greenhouse gases (e.g. biological carbon storage and sequestration; methane emissions from wetlands); Positive or negative effects on biophysical feedbacks from vegetation cover to atmosphere, such as those involving albedo, surface roughness, long-wave radiation, evapotranspiration (including moisture-recycling) and cloud formation; Direct and indirect processes involving biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOC), and regulation of aerosols and aerosol precursors by terrestrial plants and phytoplankton

Regulation of ocean acidification: Regulation, by photosynthetic organisms (on land or in water), of atmospheric CO₂ concentrations and so seawater pH, which affects associated calcification processes by many marine organisms important to humans (such as corals)

Regulation of freshwater quantity, location and timing: Regulation, by ecosystems, of the quantity, location and timing of the flow of surface and groundwater used for drinking, irrigation, transport, hydropower, and as the support of non-material contributions (NCP 15, 16, 17); Regulation of flow to water-dependent natural habitats that in turn positively or negatively affect people downstream, including via flooding (wetlands including ponds, rivers, lakes, swamps); Modification of groundwater levels, which can ameliorate dryland salinization in unirrigated landscapes

Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality: Regulation – through filtration of particles, pathogens, excess nutrients, and other chemicals – by ecosystems or particular organisms, of the quality of water used directly (e.g. drinking, swimming) or indirectly (e.g. aquatic foods, irrigated food and fiber crops, freshwater and coastal habitats of heritage value)

Formation, protection and decontamination of soils and sediments: Formation and long-term maintenance of soil structure and processes by plants and soil organisms. Includes: physical protection of soil and sediments from erosion, and supply of organic matter and nutrients by vegetation; processes that underlie the continued fertility of soils important to humans (e.g. decomposition and nutrient cycling); filtration, fixation, attenuation or storage of chemical and biological pollutants (pathogens, toxics, excess nutrients) in soils and sediments

Regulation of hazards and extreme events: Amelioration, by ecosystems, of the impacts on humans or their infrastructure caused by e.g. floods, wind, storms, hurricanes, heat waves, tsunamis, high noise levels, fires, seawater intrusion, tidal waves; Reduction or increase, by ecosystems or particular organisms, of hazards like landslides, avalanches

Regulation of detrimental organisms and biological processes:

Regulation, by organisms, of pests, pathogens, predators or competitors that affect humans (materially and nonmaterially), or plants or animals of importance for humans.

Also the direct detrimental effect of organisms on humans or their plants, animals or infrastructure. These include e.g.: Control by predators or parasites of the population size of animals important to humans, such as attacks by large carnivores, or infestation by liver fluke, on game or livestock); Regulation (by impediment or facilitation) of the abundance or distribution of potentially harmful organisms (e.g. venomous, toxic, allergenic, predators, parasites, competitors, pathogens, agricultural weeds and pests, disease vectors and reservoirs) over the landscape or seascape ; Removal, by scavengers, of animal carcasses and human corpses (e.g. vultures in Zoroastrian and some Tibetan Buddhist traditions); Biological impairment and degradation of infrastructure (e.g. damage by pigeons, bats, termites, strangling figs to buildings); Direct physical damage to crops, forest plantations, livestock, poultry and fisheries by mammals, birds and reptiles; Damage caused by invertebrates as pests of agriculture, horticulture, forest, and stored products, and by affecting health of domestic animals; Direct damage caused by organisms to humans by e.g. frightening, hurting, killing, or transmitting diseases; Regulation of the human immune system by a diverse environmental microbiota

Energy: Production of biomass-based fuels, such as biofuel crops, animal waste, fuelwood, agricultural residue pellets, peat

Food and feed: Production of food from wild , managed, or domesticated organisms, such as fish, bushmeat and edible invertebrates, beef, poultry, game, dairy products, edible crops, wild plants, mushrooms, honey; Production of feed (forage and fodder) for domesticated animals (e.g. livestock, work and support animals, pets) or for aquaculture, from the same sources

Materials, companionship and labor: Production of materials derived from organisms in cultivated or wild ecosystems, for construction, clothing, printing, ornamental purposes (e.g. wood, peat, fibers, waxes, paper, resins, dyes, pearls, shells, coral branches); Live organisms being directly used for decoration (i.e. ornamental plants, birds, fish in households and public spaces), company (e.g. pets), transport, and labor (including herding, searching, guidance, guarding)

Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources: Production of materials derived from organisms (plants, animals, fungi, microbes) used for medicinal, veterinary and pharmacological (e.g. poisonous, psychoactive) purposes. Production of genes and genetic information used for plant and animal breeding and biotechnology

Learning and inspiration: Provision, by landscapes, seascapes, habitats or organisms, of opportunities for the development of the capabilities that allow humans to prosper through education, acquisition of knowledge and development of skills for well-being, information, and inspiration for art and technological design (e.g. biomimicry)

Physical and psychological experiences: Provision, by landscapes, seascapes, habitats or organisms, of opportunities for physically and psychologically beneficial activities, healing, relaxation, recreation, leisure, tourism and aesthetic enjoyment based on the close contact with nature (e.g. hiking, recreational hunting and fishing, birdwatching, snorkeling, diving, gardening)

Supporting identities: Landscapes, seascapes, habitats or organisms being the basis for religious, spiritual, and social-cohesion experiences: Provisioning of opportunities by nature for people to develop a sense of place, belonging, rootedness or connectedness, associated with different entities of the living world (e. g. cultural, sacred and heritage landscapes, sounds, scents and sights associated with childhood experiences, iconic animals, trees or flowers); Basis for narratives, rituals and celebrations provided by landscapes, seascapes, habitats, species or organisms; Source of satisfaction derived from knowing that a particular landscape, seascape, habitat or species exists

Maintenance of options: Capacity of ecosystems, habitats, species or genotypes to keep options open in order to support a good quality of life. Examples include: Benefits (including those of future generations) associated with the continued existence of a wide variety of species, populations and genotypes. This includes their contributions to the resilience and resistance of ecosystem properties in the face of environmental change and variability; Future benefits (or threats) derived from keeping options open for yet unknown discoveries and unanticipated uses of particular organisms or ecosystems that

already exist (e.g. new medicines or materials); Future benefits (or threats) that may be anticipated from ongoing biological evolution (e.g. adaptation to a warmer climate, to emergent diseases, development of resistance to antibiotics and other control agents by pathogens and weeds)

Check all that apply.

- habitat creation and maintenance
- pollination and dispersal of seeds and other propagules
- regulation of air quality
- regulation of climate
- regulation of ocean acidification
- regulation of freshwater quantity, location, and timing
- regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality
- formation, protection, and decontamination of soils and sediments
- regulation of hazards and extreme events
- regulation of detrimental organisms and biological processes
- energy
- food and feed
- materials, companionship, and labor
- medicinal, biochemical, and genetic resources
- learning and inspiration
- physical and psychological experiences
- supporting identities
- maintenance of options

10. Underpinning value *

(Existing typology from IPBES values assessment chapter 2)

Intrinsic value: Values of natural entities as ends in-and-of themselves, expressed without reference to people as valuers

Relational value: Values of meaningful, in principle non-substitutable relationships between people and natural entities, and amongst people through nature

Instrumental value: Values of in principle substitutable natural entities as a means to human ends or to satisfy human preferences

Mark only one oval.

- Intrinsic value
- Relational value
- Instrumental value
- None

11. Cross-cutting issues *

<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

Check all that apply.

- SDG1: No poverty
- SDG2: Zero hunger
- SDG3: Good health and well-being
- SDG4: Quality education
- SDG5: Gender equality
- SDG6: Clean water and sanitation
- SDG7: Affordable and clean energy
- SDG8: Decent work and economic growth
- SDG9: Industry, innovation, and infrastructure
- SDG10: Reduced inequalities
- SDG11: Sustainable cities and communities
- SDG12: Responsible consumption and production
- SDG13: Climate action
- SDG14: Life below water
- SDG15: Life on land
- SDG16: Peace, justice, and strong institutions
- SDG17: Partnerships for the goals

12. Holistic potential *

Number of SDGs addressed (i.e., checked in previous question)

13. Evidence of use *

Mark only one oval.

- Proposed
- Case-study / pilot test
- Fully implemented as proposed by users

14. Transformative capacities *

(From Values Assessment Table 6.2)

Check all that apply.

- Addresses status quo
- Incorporates diverse values
- Fosters institutional change
- Promotes capacities
- Integrative and adaptive
- None

15. Transformative potential *

Number of transformative elements addressed (i.e., checked in previous question)

16. Dimensions of inclusivity *

Check all that apply.

- Includes ILK?
- Is it participatory?
- Multilingual?
- Does it address gender issues?
- None

17. Inclusivity potential *

Number of inclusivity dimensions addressed (i.e., checked in previous question)

18. Operationalizing costs *

If costs and technical capacity are different, choose higher option.

Mark only one oval.

- Low costs, low technical capacity
- High costs and/or technical capacity
- Unknown

19. Source *

Public online reference link, if available. If not available, list N/A.

20. Internal reference *

Internal link to working reference document from this folder: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1we-HymxwYUqeRb7cqXU1Xom2RDAXzYr4?usp=drive_link

21. Search process *

Mark only one oval.

- Scientific literature review
- Gray literature review
- Snowball
- ILK call

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